

Supplementary material to

Gas equilibrium in the H₂O-H₂-CO₂-CO-CH₄ system for wet-steam geothermal-well fluids and their sources: a case study from Krafla, Iceland

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Sampling and analysis of liquid phases from wet-steam geothermal wells

Liquid samples from geothermal well discharges were collected through a mini Webre separator connected to the two-phase pipeline close to the wellhead. We collected up to four samples after circulating the separated liquid in a stainless-steel coil submerged in cold water to reduce its temperature. All liquid samples were filtered through a 0.45 μm cellulose filter and collected in high-density polyethylene and glass bottles. The first and second samples were collected in 100 mL polyethylene bottles for major cations (Na, K, Ca, Mg, and NH_4) and anions (F, Cl, SO_4 , Br, and NO_3) analyses. For cation analyses, the liquid sample was treated with 0.2 mL of 1 M HNO_3 solution. Since sulphide sulfur may oxidize to SO_4 increasing the initial SO_4 concentration in the second sample, it was precipitated by adding 0.5 mL of a 2 M $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ solution, and removed by filtration (Arnórsson et al., 2000). The third liquid sample was collected into a 300 mL glass bottle where 1 mL of 10 N NaOH solution was added for dissolved CO_2 and H_2S analyses. The fourth sample was collected in a 100 mL plastic bottle and diluted 1:10 with ultrapure water for SiO_2 analysis.

Cation (Na, K, Ca, Mg, and NH_4) and anion (F, Cl, SO_4 , Br, and NO_3) concentrations in the first and second samples of the well liquid phases, reinjection water (Table S3), and steam condensates (Table S4) were measured using a Dionex ICS-3000 ion chromatograph at the Laboratory of the Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Sezione di Napoli, Osservatorio Vesuviano (INGV-OV). Those of K-21 and K-30 wells were analyzed by ion chromatography at the Laboratory of Landsvirkjun at Krafla, where the following analyses of sample three and four were also carried out. The alkaline solution in the third sample was analyzed for H_2S and CO_2 concentrations (Table S3) on the same day of sampling using titration (Metrohm 907, Tritando), following standard procedures (Arnórsson et al., 2006). SiO_2 concentration (Table S1) in the fourth sample was determined using the molybdate yellow method with an absorbance spectrophotometer (Hach Lange DR 3900).

Supplemental Figures

Figure S1: Measured enthalpy of the total well discharges (h_d) plotted against the enthalpy of the total discharges calculated through an enthalpy balance ($h_{d,c}$) based on the temperatures and fraction of equilibrium vapor (y_e) estimated through the $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{H}_2-\text{CO}_2-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_4$ gas system for wet-steam well fluids (see Table 3).

Figure S2: Theoretical grids in the $\log(X_{CO}/X_{H_2})$ vs. $3\log(X_{CO}/X_{CO_2}) + \log(X_{CO}/X_{CH_4})$ space describing coexistence of an equilibrium vapor and liquid phase in the geothermal reservoir. The black grid was constructed using the P_{CO_2} - T dependence derived in this study (eq. 25), whereas the grey grids describe the P_{CO_2} - T dependence fixed by the mineral buffer including clinozoisite-calcite-quartz-phrenite (Stefansson and Arnorsson, 2002; Table S2) with activity of clinozoisite of 0.3 and 1. The total discharge from K-21 appears to be explained by this mineral buffer within the range of a_{czo} reported.

Supplemental Tables

Table S1: Logarithm of vapor-liquid distribution coefficients (log B) and equilibrium constants (log K) dependencies on temperature, with t in °C and T in K. See *section 3.4* for further details.

$$\log B_{CO_2} = 4.7593 - 0.01092 \times t \quad (1)$$

$$\log B_{H_2S} = 4.0547 - 0.00981 \times t \quad (2)$$

$$\log B_{Ar} = 6.4822 - 0.016 \times t \quad (3)$$

$$\log B_{N_2} = 6.4426 - 0.01416 \times t \quad (4)$$

$$\log B_{CH_4} = 6.0783 - 0.01383 \times t \quad (5)$$

$$\log B_{H_2} = 6.2283 - 0.01403 \times t \quad (6)$$

$$\log B_{He} = 6.3650 - 0.01451 \times t \quad (7)$$

$$\log B_{CO} = 6.3173 - 0.01388 \times t \quad (8)$$

$$\log K_{H_2} = 2.548 - \frac{12,707}{T} \quad (9)$$

$$\log K_{CO} = 5.033 - \frac{14,955}{T} \quad (10)$$

$$\log K_{RWG} = 2.485 - \frac{2,248}{T} \quad (11)$$

$$\log K_{CCC} = 19.605 - \frac{17,813}{T} \quad (12)$$

$$\log K_{SS4} = -\frac{258,773.6}{T^2} + \frac{10,176.6}{T} - 11.37445 \quad (13)$$

$$\log K_{RWG,l} = 3.279477 \times 10^{-16} \times t^6 - 4.78832 \times 10^{-13} \times t^5 + 3.002675 \times 10^{-10} \times t^4 - 1.089417 \times 10^{-7} \times t^3 + 2.582843 \times 10^{-5} \times t^2 - 2.944894 \times 10^{-3} \times t - 3.448121 \quad (14)$$

(1, 2, 4–6) Giggenbach, 1980; (3, 7) this study, calculated through the eq. 16 of Fernandez-Prini et al., 2003; (8) Bertrami et al., 1985; (9–12) Chiodini and Marini, 1998; (13) Marini et al., 2022; (14) this study, computed through SUPCRT92 (Johnson et al, 1992) using the thermodynamic database of Chase (1998), and fitted through a polynomial curve.

Table S2: Dependence of the logarithm of the partial pressure of CO₂ (log P_{CO₂}) on temperature, with t in °C and T in K. See section 3.4.1 for further details.

$$a_{CZO}=1$$

$$\log P_{CO_2} = 1.996140 \times 10^{-13} \times t^5 - 4.558037 \times 10^{-10} \times t^4 + 3.565688 \times 10^{-07} \times t^3 - 1.517499 \times 10^{-04} \times t^2 + 4.428150 \times 10^{-2} \times t - 5.067291 \quad (1)$$

$$a_{CZO}=0.3$$

$$\log P_{CO_2} = 1.324985 \times 10^{-12} \times t^5 - 1.131579 \times 10^{-9} \times t^4 + 3.673950 \times 10^{-7} \times t^3 - 9.039603 \times 10^{-5} \times t^2 + 3.152012 \times 10^{-2} \times t - 4.852342$$

(2)

$$\log P_{CO_2} = 3.573 - \frac{46}{T} + \log \left(\frac{X_{CO}}{X_{H_2}} \right)$$

(1) Stefánsson and Arnórsson, 2002; (2) Chiodini and Cioni, 1989.

Table S3: Chemical (mg kg^{-1}) and isotopic composition of the vapor and liquid phase ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ in ‰ vs. V-SMOW) of the wet-steam well fluids collected at the separator. The pressure and temperature in the separator (P_s and T_s), as well as the mass flow (\dot{m}), total discharge enthalpy (h_d) of the wells, and the vapor fraction (y) are also reported. All the analyses were carried out at the laboratory of the INGV-OV, Italy, except SiO_2 , H_2S , and CO_2 in the liquid phases, which were analyzed in the Krafla laboratory by Landsvirkjun by the end of the day of sample collection. The chemical composition of the liquid phase of K-21 and K-30, pH, and T of the liquid phase were also measured by Landsvirkjun.

Sample	Date	Sampling conditions					Vapor phase (mg kg^{-1})										
		P_s [bar]	T_s [°C]	\dot{m} [kg s^{-1}]	h_d [kJ kg^{-1}]	y	H_2O	CO_2	H_2S	Ar	N_2	CH_4	H_2	He	CO	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$
K-19	08/29/2023	9.5	177.8	4.2	2671	0.948	994000	5400	696	1.60	50.5	0.77	46.8	0.00369	0.0639	-12.1	-90.7
K-20	08/31/2023	9.0	175.4	4.5	2636	0.932	985000	13200	1180	1.87	60.4	2.76	57.8	0.0182	0.127	-12.2	-89.9
K-21	08/30/2023	10.8	183.2	45.4	1113	0.168	998000	1680	208	3.15	101	10.2	0.8	0.0036	0.0250	-14.2	-97.8
K-27	08/28/2023	9.3	176.7	37.8	1092	0.170	998000	2010	216	2.64	83.7	3.42	5.3	0.0061	0.028	-13.9	-91.3
K-30	08/28/2023	10.6	182.5	14.3	2583	0.902	993000	5680	1230	1.40	46.1	0.50	51.2	0.00722	0.0465	-11.3	-89.0
K-31	08/25/2023	8.0	170.6	0.6	2781	1	994000	5260	949	1.84	62.4	0.61	55.8	0.0428	0.1	-12.4	-93.0
K-32	08/29/2023	7.8	169.4	48.0	1095	0.185	998000	1710	470	2.16	71.3	1.65	5.4	0.00483	0.0377	-13.7	-92.9
K-34	08/30/2023	9.0	175.4	14.9	2236	0.735	994000	4790	1510	1.52	48	0.62	39.9	0.0128	0.0376	-10.9	-87.9
K-36	08/28/2023	9.0	175.4	10.2	2607	0.918	991000	7040	1840	1.25	40.2	0.72	46.5	0.00587	0.0975	-10.8	-90.8
K-38	08/28/2023	8.0	170.4	8.9	2035	0.642	991000	7190	1370	1.97	61.7	1.71	30.6	0.00756	0.108	-12.5	-90.3
K-40	08/24/2023	11.0	184.0	18.6	2762	0.991	985000	13700	1060	2.30	77	1.57	21.2	0.0115	0.1	-11.7	-89.9
K-41	08/24/2023	10.0	179.9	6.3	2729	0.976	986000	12400	990	1.45	49	1.50	44.7	0.0228	0.0855	-11.9	-88.9

Table S3 (continued)

Sample	Liquid phase (mg kg ⁻¹)															
	pH/T[°C]	SiO ₂	Na	NH ₄	K	Mg	Ca	F	Cl	SO ₄	NO ₃	Br	H ₂ S	CO ₂	δ ¹⁸ O _{H2O}	δD _{H2O}
K-19	8.33 / 22.3	755	139		25.9	0.19	7.83	4.03	60.8	82.2	n.a.	1.58	65.3	90.3	-9.8	-88.2
K-20	8.4 / 8.9	796	229		35.8	0.07	6.62	1.62	154	87.7	n.a.	2.39	96	154	-10.0	-88.0
K-21	9.11 / 19.7	615	207		30.7		0.96	1.19	212	65.1	n.a.	0.72	34.8	14.1	-13.8	-97.1
K-27	9.42 / 23.3	521	234		28.1		15.5	0.80	32.4	334	n.a.	3.29	44.3	62.1	-11.3	-87.5
K-30	8.09 / 27.1	701	170		31.8		0.66	2.60	170	35.9	n.a.	0.20	73.7	51.8	-11.0	-90.2
K-32	8.95 / 25.7	588	252	1.8	37.1	0.02	13.7	0.90	42.4	328	n.a.	6.93	94.9	49.5	-11.1	-87.5
K-34	8.25 / 20.4	642	199	0.86	31.3	0.08	7.19	1.51	114	135	n.a.	2.10	118	73.5	-8.7	-85.3
K-36	7.85 / 20	733	179		32.7	0.18	6.08	0.79	141	83	n.a.	2.49	106	77	-8.6	-88.2
K-38	8.05 / 27.1	515	165		19.7	0.12	8.39	0.96	48.4	158	n.a.	2.01	103	89.3	-10.2	-88.5
K-40	7.51 / 25.8	584	67	0.61	13.3	0.09	4.85	2.10	5.0	25.9	n.a.	0.21	109	641	-9.6	-85.9
K-41	8.32 / 15.6	751	167	0.63	25.0	0.02	6.03	1.37	67.7	80.4	n.a.	1.77	82.7	139	-9.8	-87.0
Reinjection fluid (K-26)	n.a. / 12.0	n.a.	250		33.2		13	0.92	89.8	246	14.96	3.18	n.a.	n.a.	-10.5	-85.7

Sample	Steam condensate (mg kg ⁻¹)								
	Na	NH ₄	K	Mg	Ca	F	Cl	SO ₄	Br
K-19	0.12	0.17	0.06	0	0.17	0.0008	0.0104	0.88	0.0126
K-20	0.3	0.21	0.16		0.18	0.001	0.0213	1.22	n.a.
K-21	0.19	0.23	0.06	0	0.2	0.0006	0.0164	0.94	0.0114
K-27	5.31	0.29	0.14	0.01	0.24	0.0018	0.127	10.3	0.0253
K-30	0.25	0.1	0.08	0	0.12	0.0029	0.0179	1.21	0.0057
K-31	0.32	0.18	0.1	0.02	0.15	0.0007	0.0242	1.68	0.0055
K-32	0.18	0.16	0.04		0.18	n.a.	0.0132	1.17	0.0101
K-34	0.2	0.11	0.12		0.16	0.0004	0.193	1.37	0.0037
K-36	0.61	0.11	0.3	0.01	0.26	0.0007	0.181	3.32	0.0203
K-38	0.8	0.13	0.26		0.29	0.0008	0.0263	2.33	0.0104
K-40	1.01	0.18	0.2	0	0.19	0.0044	0.12	1.49	n.a.
K-41	0.71	0.13	0.12	0	0.14	n.a.	0.0961	0.83	0.0076

Table S4: Chemical composition (mg kg⁻¹) of fumarole steam condensates.

Sample	Steam condensate (mg kg ⁻¹)								
	Na	NH ₄	K	Mg	Ca	F	Cl	SO ₄	Br
LKJ1	0.23	0.02	0.04	0	0.15	0.0003	0.012	0.69	0.0083
SUD1	0.35	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.20	0.0003	0.331	1.26	0.0061
SUD2	0.09	0.85	0.06	0.01	0.12	n.a.	0.037	7.14	0.870

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